

made in 1978. FARO 49 is ITA315 line, selected in F₆ from a single cross made in 1979. It involved parents such as Sigadis, TN1, Peta, Dee-geo-woo-gen, CP-SLO, and Iguape Cateto.

All five varieties are resistant to leaf blast. FARO 45 and FARO 46 are resistant to leaf scald. These are the

major problems affecting upland rice in Nigeria. FARO 45 and FARO 46 also have drought tolerance and escape drought damage because they mature early.

The lines were evaluated in multi-locational coordinated rice evaluation trials (CRET) in Nigeria. After 3 yr of

superior performances in these trials, they were evaluated in farmers' fields. The varieties are location-specific. FARO 45 is not suited for the acidic uplands of the humid forest zone. The WARDA Lowland Rice Breeding Unit at IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, is producing breeder seed of all varieties. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—flood-prone

Saraswati and Jalaprabha: two new deepwater rice varieties for eastern India

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The State Variety Release Committee, West Bengal, approved the release of two varieties, Saraswati (CN584-311-10) and Jalaprabha for deepwater ecosystems (50-100 cm) in June 1996. Saraswati is a pedigree selection from the cross Pankaj/Patnai 23, done at RRS. It was evaluated as IET11271 in national trials during 1989-94 (Table 1). The pooled average yield across 36 locations was 50% more than national check Utkal Prabha. In national testing, it ranked fourth in the 1989 preliminary variety trial, eighth in the 1993 advanced variety trial-semideep water, and second in the 1994 advanced variety trial-semideep water, tested over 13 locations. The variety's mean yield was 2.7 t ha⁻¹ with yield potential of 4.6 t ha⁻¹. The All-India Rice Workshop suggested it for use in the deepwater areas of Assam, West Bengal, Andhra Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Orissa.

Saraswati is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the end of October. Its submergence tolerance is mainly through elongation, and it has very good kneeing ability. Panicles are well exerted with short, bold golden grains and purple apiculi. Kernels are about 5.5 × 2.6 mm. Hulling percentage is 78.5 and milling percentage is 68.5.

Table 1. Performance of Saraswati in national trials in India. 1989-94.

Year	Trial ^a /site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Saraswati	Utkal Prabha	
1989	PVT5			
	Patna, Bihar	4.5 ^b	2.1	65
	Pusa, Bihar	4.6	3.7	55
	Karimganj, Assam	2.6	2.4	25
	Pulla, Andhra Pradesh	4.3	2.6	80
1990	IVT-SDW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.8 ^b	Nil	70
	Sabour, Bihar	3.7	3.2	na ^c
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	2.0 ^b	1.2	na
	Canning, West Bengal	4.2 ^b	Nil	na
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	3.5	3.3	na
1991	AVT-SDW			
	Ranital, Orissa	2.1 ^a	1.8	na
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	3.6 ^b	2.3	65
	Karimganj, Assam	3.2	2.3	na
	Patna, Bihar	1.9	1.5	na
	Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	1.1	0.5	na
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	2.0	1.3	na
1992	AVT-SDW			
	Pulla, Andhra Pradesh	1.5	1.4	60
	CRR1, Orissa	1.7	1.4	100
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.2 ^b	0.2	55
	Sabour, Bihar	2.4	2.4	45
	Karimganj, Assam	4.1 ^b	3.5	25
1993	AVT-SDW			
	CRR1, Orissa	1.6 ^b	0.7	na
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	4.1 ^b	1.6	75
	Patna, Bihar	2.9	2.2	na
	Pusa, Bihar	1.10	Nil	75
	Sabour, Bihar	2.7 ^b	1.9	na
	Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	3.1 ^b	2.3	30
	Karimganj, Assam	3.9	3.8	31
1994	AVT-SDW			
	Ranital, Orissa	2.5 ^b	1.3	50
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	2.5 ^b	1.1	50
	Gosaba, West Bengal	3.5	2.9	50
	Patna, Bihar	1.7	1.5	na
	Sabour, Bihar	2.3 ^b	0.7	na
	Masodha, Uttar Pradesh	3.2 ^b	1.8	60
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	1.7	1.5	50
	Canning, West Bengal	2.9	2.6	na
		Karimganj, Assam	2.6 ^b	2.1

^a PVT 5 = preliminary variety trial 5, IVT-SDW = initial variety trial-semideepwater, AVT-SDW = advanced variety trial-semideepwater.

^b Significantly superior to national check at the 5% level. ^c na = not available.

Table 2. Performance of Jalaprabha in national trials in India. 1989-94.

Year	Trial ^a /site	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Maximum water depth (cm)
		Jalaprabha	Jalamagna	
1989	PVT6			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.9 ^b	nil	65
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	2.1 ^b	1.2	110
1990	IVT-DW			
	Pusa, Bihar	2.5	2.4	na ^c
	North Lakhimpur, Assam	4.1 ^b	2.6	na
1991	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.8 ^b	0.5	95
	Pusa, Bihar	3.4 ^b	2.2	na
1992	AVT-DW			
	Motto, Orissa	2.4	1.7	125
	Ghagrahat, Uttar Pradesh	3.7	2.7	141
1993	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	1.6 ^b	0.6	100
1994	AVT-DW			
	Chinsurah, West Bengal	4.0 ^b	0.9	80
	Pusa, Bihar	3.8 ^b	2.5	na
	Motto, Orissa	2.8 ^b	2.4	na

^aPVT 6 = preliminary variety trial 6, IVT-DW = initial variety trial-deepwater, AVT-DW = advanced variety trial-deepwater. ^bSignificantly superior to national check at the 5% level. ^cna = not available.

Both alkali value (6.5) and amylose content (30.0) are high.

Saraswati has resistance to blast, sheath blight, sheath rot, yellow stem borer, and whitebacked planthopper.

Jalaprabha was developed by pedigree selection from a composite cross sent by IRRI and evaluated as IET11870 in the national varietal testing program for several years (Table 2). The pooled

averages across 12 locations yielded 73% more than check Jalamagna. The variety's yield potential is 4.1 t ha⁻¹. In national testing, it ranked second in the 1990 initial variety trial-deepwater, first in the 1991 advanced variety trial-deepwater, third in the 1993 advanced trial-deepwater, and first in the 1994 advanced variety trial-deepwater. The All-India Rice Workshop in 1995 recommended it for the eastern Indian states of West Bengal, Orissa, Bihar, and Uttar Pradesh.

Jalaprabha is tall, photoperiod-sensitive, and flowers around the first week of November. Its submergence tolerance is mainly through elongation, and it has very good kneeing ability. Panicles are compact and well exerted with short, bold, golden grains. Kernels are about 5.6 × 2.4 mm. Hulling percentage is 78.8 and milling percentage is 64.1. Both alkali value (7.0) and amylose content (29.2) are high. Seed dormancy is about 3 mo.

It has tolerance for yellow stem borer, leaffolder, sheath rot, sheath blight, blast, and false smut. ■

Seed technology

Nucleus and breeder seed production of thermosensitive genic male sterile lines

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Thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines are suitable for developing two-line hybrids in the tropics because temperature variations are found in different seasons and/or locations for maintaining effective sterility and fertility. Research efforts by IRRI and national agricultural research systems (NARS) have resulted in identifying many TGMS lines from four to five sources that can be deployed for developing two-line hybrids. Production of good-quality

pure seed of TGMS lines is a prerequisite for successful use of these lines.

Experience in China has indicated that TGMS lines multiplied conventionally by bulking their seeds at a fertility-inducing temperature may tend to segregate for their critical sterility /fertility points. Seed obtained from such lines may not be pure. These lines, when used to produce two-line hybrid seeds, could be a mixture of selfed and hybrid seeds, resulting in unstable hybrids. Nucleus and breeder seed production strategies should, therefore, aim to meet the dual objectives of maintaining complete male sterility during hybrid seed production and higher seed set during TGMS multiplication. We describe here a simple method of producing nucleus

and breeder seed of TGMS lines under field conditions.

Seasons / locations suitable for TGMS multiplication and hybrid seed production must be identified based on weather data and the behavior of selected TGMS lines. For example, at IRRI, flowering of TGMS lines in January and February induces fertility and is ideal for multiplication, whereas flowering from mid April to May induces complete male sterility, a condition necessary for hybrid seed production. The proposed method shown in the figure will produce nucleus and breeder seed of TGMS lines.

Nucleus seed production of a TGMS line is initiated in a fertility-inducing environment. Seeding of TGMS lines is